

Physics and extraterrestrial Linguistics throughout the cosmos, how do different types of symbols and spacing in ‘languages’ and different extraterrestrial notation display the same underlying physical mechanics?

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Introduction

First of all this work concerns itself with mechanics and how it would be representable throughout the cosmos, i.e. exoplanets in the habitable zone or moons of gas giants that happen to have geological activity and water, hycean worlds. Or floaters and hunters on gas giants, like Cal Sagan, when pushed to, used to imagine in his book *Cosmos* (Sagan, 1980).

The physical limitations are that the mechanics of language are bound to the biology of the creature speaking a ‘language’. One could also describe it as sound-responce-at-a-distance between any two creatures of the same species that belong to a local-population that possesses a sound based communication system that works in locally but not necessarily globally in other populations of the same species at different locations. The communication is also limited to the speed of sound specific to the medium and the biology of the individual creature. The medium could be fluid water (in which case the speed of sound is several times faster than in air), or a mixture of gases (in which case the speed of sound is less than in water). If it is a gas atmosphere there could be thinner (in which case there is a slower speed of sound) or a thicker (in which case there is a faster speed of sound) or almost equal atmospheres (in which case there would be an almost equal speed of sound) to the one we are used to on our earth.

The linguistic limitations overlap somewhat with the physical ones regarding the biology of the creatures. But the two main distinctions will be how the language is represented.

We either encounter the first category, being phonographical systems and the second category being pictorial or logographic symbols.

Both require binocular vision and sophisticated hand-eye coordination. The same would be likely for sophisticated tentacle-eye coordination. We are really limited to examples we know from our own planet and its inhabitants here and it will be easy to drift off into speculation. As Richard Feynman said: «The first principle is that you must not fool yourself and you are the easiest person to fool.». There may be limbs we even can't imagine that enable a creature to use tools. Tool-use is the major premise that must be fulfilled to write down a 'spoken language' or sound-response-at-a-distance between any two creatures of the same kind that belong to a population that possesses a sound based communication system. It is the first premise because the ability to use tools, enables creatures of a population to store information extraneously. Extraneously information storage enables a language to be non-local.

If a language is not extraneously stored it is only locally valid. Reflecting in the different dialects of languages in local areas that over time became different languages. And the fact that the extraneous storage enables a language to become non-locally valid.

«Roman Latin did not have local dialectical variations; Rome was a more hierarchical and administratively centred, and learning and influence was the privilege of a marked upper class. By 100 CE the various Italian languages had been subsumed by Latin and as the Roman Empire spread so Latin took the place of indigenous languages as occurred in France, Spain and Portugal.» (Janson, 2012)

First we have to think about where extraneous storage of information (writing and reading) is physically possible. Is it possible under water. Yes it is if creatures have tentacles, but also it requires enough light such that it can be readable by others, hence it won't be happening on an icy-moon with liquid water under its surface. It is covered under ice and likely further from its respective host-star and hence simply too dark (infrared vision is unlikely because symbols are not staying warm because of the heat loss, although the moment of carving or drawing would enable temporary heat signatures from the friction that also such a world would display).

The only planets that enable writing and reading, at least as we are limited to know it, are planets in the habitable zone with liquid water that inhabit tool using creatures above the dark-zone in their oceans and tool using creatures on their land masses that develop their tool-usage so far as to being capable of reading and writing and teaching those skills to the next generations.

Gas giants with floaters and hunters like Carl Sagan's imagined them likely also fall out of the equation because there likely are no floating pebbles or pigments to carve or write onto something in a gaseous atmosphere. Even though communication could happen very well via sound.

Potential relational symbols

We have to think of abstract symbols that are necessary to describe mathematical and hence physical and linguistic relations. Those symbols are not required in written or readable form in order for 'language' to arise.

But if written and read language is has developed, the ability to describe physical and hence mathematical relations co-exists. The cognition of a creature may be able to think in proto-mathematical terms even without 'language', but is not able to communicate it effectively with other creatures without 'language'.

Any symbols are a distinction from a background. But also distinctive relative to each other. This can be achieved by creating pictorial symbols of things like people did with hieroglyphs in ancient Egypt or logographsics as Chinese has and which can be combined into words and sentences. Another way would be letters that can be combined into words and sentences as phonographic languages (most languages nowadays) do. Assuming the exoplanet has different non-global (lingua-fracta analoga) but local 'languages' or as we previously defined as sound-responsiveness-at-a-distance between any two creatures of the same species that belong to a local-population that possesses a sound based communication system that works in locally but not necessarily globally in other populations of the same species at different locations.

It is concisely the mathematical notation we want to think of:

equal to $\bullet\bullet \equiv =$ thus $(x \bullet\bullet y) \equiv (x = y)$

not equal to $\bullet\circ \equiv \neq$ thus $(x \bullet\circ y) \equiv (x \neq y)$

greater than or equal to $\circ \equiv \geq$ thus $(x \circ y) \equiv (x \geq y)$

lesser than or equal to $\odot \equiv \leq$ thus $(x \odot y) \equiv (x \leq y)$

greater than $\swarrow \equiv >$ thus $(x \swarrow y) \equiv (x > y)$

lesser than $\searrow \equiv <$ thus $(x \searrow y) \equiv (x < y)$

Here greater than ' \swarrow ' and lesser than ' \searrow ' are reasonable to think of because any exoplanet that we reasoned ourselves towards to, providing it enables reading and writing as we humans know it, must lie in the habitable zone. And exoplanets in the habitable zone are either of comparable size as our Earth or so called super-Earths «a class of planets unlike any in our solar system - are more massive than Earth yet lighter than ice giants like Neptune and Uranus, and can be made of gas, rock or a combination of both. They are between twice the size of Earth and up to 10 times its mass.» (NASA, u.d.). So they must be able to weigh objects against one another on a scale-like device which they made. That is a massive amount of premisses that need to be true in order for this to hold. Which is a huge limitation that we acknowledge.

Mecahnical equations in phonographic symbols and in logographic symbols and their deviance

Newton's second law is stated in English phonographic symbols F for force, m for mass and a for acceleration as the reader surely knows:

$$F = ma$$

Now if Newtons second law was to be stated with Chinese logographic symbols it would look as follows:

$$\text{力} = \text{质量} \text{ 加速度}$$

Of course the chinese do not use their own-symbols and they use the exact same letters F, m and a for every term as the english and other nations do. Because we require global coherence. That has nothing to do with of any language, chinese just happens to be one of the best and modern examples of a logographic language that we know how to translate.

There is no problem in writing it the chinese way if one knows how to translate it.

Alien civilizations may know how to translate their languages, but we dont. We would require a Rosetta-Stone in order to do so. And here lies one of the biggest deviations between phonographic and logographic languages. Mass has one symbol in a phonographic language, that being m. While mass has two symbols in chinese those being 质量 which roughly translates literally into 'add speed' bu tare translated as 'mass'. For acceleration english has one word and one letter, that being a. Chinese on the other hand has three, those being 加速度 which roughly translate literally into 'quality quantity' bu tare translated as 'acceleration'.

This would lead to problems translating it only if there was no space inbetween 质量 and 加速度, but there is in fact a space, a space which enables us to see it as a unit or a word for something. This would not be the case in polysynthetic languages. Polysynthetic languages for describing mechanics would be a cosmic nightmare for everybody that wishes to obtain a translation. Because in order to know where one word ends and another one begins, one had to have knowledge of the language to begin with.

It would not be the biggest problem to translate a logographical alien language based mechanics into a phonographical based language mechanics, provided one has a gathered or aquired a total list over all their mechanics. On earth we even agreed on a common notation, which other creatures would also have to do, provided they have a globalized planet. Without understanding each of them one could easily see, even without any knowledge of Chinese:

$$\frac{\text{力}}{\text{加速度}} = \text{质量}, \frac{\text{力}}{\text{质量}} = \text{加速度}$$

But here we quietly assume that those creatures have the same notation for multiplication and division.

Here we use our invented, but somewhat reasonably guessed relational symbols for $>$, \geq , \leq , $<$, \neq and $=$. If we want to express an apple(苹果) is equal to another apple(苹果) in our mathematical notation we would simply write:

apple=apple

Whereas in the notation from p. 3 we would write:

苹果 ●● 苹果

This notation is pretty clear.

If we want to express an apple(苹果) is unequal to a pear (梨) in our mathematical notation we would write:

apple≠pear

Whereas in the notation from p. 3 we would write:

苹果 ●○ 梨

The problem with this notation it could also be interpreted as being 'opposite of', or symmetrical to. But could be interpreted as not equal to if one first knows that ●● means 'equal to'.

If we want to express an apple(苹果) is greater or equal to a peach (桃) in our mathematical notation we would write:

apple≥peach

Whereas in the notation from p. 3 we would write:

苹果 ● 桃

The problem here being that it looks two things of some type are somehow related more than another thing of one type.

If we want to express a peach (桃) is less or equal to an apple(苹果) in our mathematical notation we would write:

$$\text{apple} \leq \text{peach}$$

Whereas in the notation from p. 3 we would write:

$$\text{桃} \circ \text{苹果}$$

The problem here being that it looks two things of some type are somehow related more than another thing of one type, but we can see it must be an inverse relationship. That is neat.

If we want to express an apple (苹果) is greater than a peach (桃) in our mathematical notation we would write:

$$\text{apple} > \text{peach}$$

Whereas in the notation from p. 3 we would write:

$$\text{苹果} \diagdown \text{桃}$$

The problem here being that it looks two things of some type are more than another thing of one type. But we see the symbol is like a scale whichs left side is further down than its right side, wich is higher up. A property that doesn't change throughout the cosmos.

But if we want to express a peach (桃) is less than an apple(苹果) in our mathematical notation we would write:

$$\text{peach} < \text{apple}$$

Whereas in the notation from p. 3 we would write:

$$\text{桃} \diagup \text{苹果}$$

The problem here being that it looks two things of some type are more than another thing of one type. But we see the symbol is like a scale whichs right side is further down than its left side, wich is higher up. A property that doesn't change throughout the cosmos.

- We draw the conclusion that the greatest issue here is not that one language is logographic and the other one phonographic. Even if a logographic symbol were to consist of several combined elements. Like 好 (good) consists of 女 (feminine/woman) and 子 (son/child) in which way there is no space inbetween, if it was a mechanical concept, the act of combining symbols would display no problem as long as the mathematical relation and operation symbols would be clear. Thus it is the mathematical notation that is important and the spacing in a symbol that makes one distinct of another one that is important. We effectively figured out that mechanics, written in most languages is translatable provided one has a full list of mechanical equations from that respective other extraterrestrial language no matter if it is phonographic or logographic, as long as it is not polysynthetic and does not possess spacings or unclear mathematical symbols for the most basic relations.

Extraterrestrial 'languages' are likely to have abstract representations that are congruent to the notion of numbers. But again it's not necessarily clear to us what those numbers mean. And here logographic languages like Chinese are distinct from Roman number representations looked like.

In Roman numbers looked like I (1), II (2), III (3), IV (4), V (5), VI (6), VII (7), VIII (8), IX (9) and X (10) and had no zero (0) term because their system was based on subtraction and addition.

Whereas the Chinese have 一(1)、二(2)、三(3)、四(4)、五(5)、六(6)、七(7)、八(8)、九(9)、十(10) and «In [] rod calculations, the absence of a unit in a specific place value was indicated simply by leaving a space – an "empty position". Like the Babylonians, this was a functional placeholder concept crucial for their positional system, but there was no explicit written symbol for zero.» (Kurbalija, 2023)

- A language has to have abstract representations that are congruent to the notion of numbers that do consist of line horizontal line segments '-' or vertical line segments 'I' or points '.', our modern number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 fail incredibly at this as did the Roman or the Chinese numbers. But at least the Chinese and the Roman had this way of expressing number from 1-3 and failed to do so from 4-9 onwards.
It would really be universally understandable if we used I, II, III, II II, II III, III III, III II II, III III, III II III, III III III and combined them in a sort of table to explain it with dots.
Like (II)(III II) ●●....., and in doing so, explaining 2 times 5 is equal to 10. But we had also come up with a universal base. How would we achieve that? One can simply not know what another creature would prefer.

Hence we had to explain the extraterrestrial creatures when we ‘collapse an amount into a whole’, i.e. when do we use a new symbol that is not any longer trivial dots and lines (which are fundamental rather than cultural).

Now the case that we humans use 0 to account for the empty-set but behind a number it works as a full-ten multiplied by that number.

Let me show it, so its easier to see what that means:

$$\begin{aligned}
 10 &= 1 \times 10 \\
 20 &= 2 \times 10 \\
 30 &= 3 \times 10 \\
 &\dots \\
 100 &= 1 \times 10 \times 10 \\
 1000 &= 1 \times 10 \times 10 \times 10 \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned}$$

And so on and so forth. So any zero, as long as there is no comma, means a whole. And since we happen to have 10 fingers, or base 10, we ‘collapse the amount into a whole’. I hope this pedagogically explained what I wanted to say with the expression ‘collapse into a whole’. But we could have used any symbol for that.

If they instead of 0 would use a square, their numbers would look like as follows, here \equiv means congruent (in everyday language \equiv could be simplified to ‘in place of’):

$$\begin{aligned}
 I \blacksquare &\equiv 10 \\
 II \blacksquare &\equiv 20 \\
 III \blacksquare &\equiv 30 \\
 &\dots \\
 I \blacksquare \blacksquare &\equiv 100 \\
 I \blacksquare \blacksquare \blacksquare &\equiv 1000 \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned}$$

It would not change anything. But in our radio-telescope or other communication message we had to specify that one square is equal to 10 things: $I \blacksquare \bullet \bullet \dots$.

But there really is no way of knowing how they would denote their base (when they, mentally or on paper, collapse a set of numbers into a whole). Important to note is that of practical reasons one has to collapse a number as one adds numbers upon it such that it gets bigger and bigger. One has to simplify huge numbers in order to handle them.

The extraterrestrial creatures indirectly explained us how they multiply. The most important thing that they have to think thereafter is how to explain us the direction of division, as division is non-commutative as well as subtraction.

It is biologically likely that their eyes are fixed and of that reason it makes the extraterrestrial creatures read from one direction to another, from left to right or from right to left (like in arabic) or from top-down or bottom-up.

The easiest way would be using an arrow (It is not clear to them we would understand it, but if we understand physics we should understand the principle of least action and hence that the arrow points into the direction towards where it experiences resistance, therefore the arrow has angles that decrease resistance like this \longrightarrow , and not increase resistance like this \longleftarrow)

They could show us:

$$10/1 = 10 \equiv \blacksquare | I \bullet\bullet \dots\dots$$

$$\frac{10}{2} = 5 \equiv \blacksquare | II \bullet\bullet \dots$$

But

$$\frac{1}{10} = 10 \equiv I | \blacksquare \bullet\bullet\bullet \dots$$

And

$$\frac{2}{1} = 2 \equiv II | I \bullet\bullet \dots$$

Whereas

$$\frac{1}{2} = 0.5 \equiv II | I \bullet\bullet \dots$$

Here they had no other way then drawing

There simply is no easier way of explaining fractions when not sharing a common-language. This means even we, if we had to communicate with them, or they with us, both of us had to be pictorial to begin with.

How would they explain us subtraction? How would we explain them subtraction?

We cannot confuse them by writing minus as a horizontal line '-' so we had to first show subtraction we could show $4 - 2 = 2 \equiv III \overset{II}{\rightarrow} II$, and provide many examples:

$$10 - 10 = 90 \equiv \blacksquare\blacksquare \overset{\blacksquare}{\rightarrow} (III \ III \ III) \blacksquare \bullet\bullet \dots\dots$$

$$5 - 2 = 3 \equiv (II \ III) \overset{II}{\rightarrow} III$$

$$50 - 5 = 40 + 5 = 45 \equiv (\text{II III}) \blacksquare \xrightarrow{\text{III II}} (((\text{III}) \blacksquare) \leftarrow \text{II III}) \bullet \bullet \dots \dots \dots$$

Now obviously this would not be the easiest way, because we had to use many parenthesis. They could simply use symbols like $\ulcorner \urcorner \equiv +$ and $\lrcorner \equiv -$ that we would very well understand if they would explain it:

$$4 - 2 = 2 \equiv \text{III} \lrcorner \urcorner \text{II} \bullet \bullet \text{II}$$

$$100 - 10 = 90 \equiv \text{I} \blacksquare \blacksquare \lrcorner \urcorner \blacksquare \bullet \bullet (\text{III III III}) \blacksquare \bullet \bullet \dots \dots \dots$$

$$\text{Or } 10 + 10 = 20 \equiv \text{I} \blacksquare \ulcorner \urcorner \text{I} \blacksquare \bullet \bullet \text{II} \blacksquare \bullet \bullet \dots \dots \dots$$

And so on and so forth. So even we were, or they were initially afraid of doing so they could use their symbols and we could use ours, as long as we would always show examples with signs explained previously and lines and dots.

More On Numerals, Symbols and Bases in Extraterrestrial Communication

One day I worked in a school and recognized that children that learned the numbers from 1-100 got a grid with the numbers from 1-100. My focus was on the grid and the assumption behind it. There were year-thousands of knowledge behind this little grid.

It looked almost like the following graphic:

confusion and counting again in order to be certain. The mind has to chunk information. It has to collapse them into symbols. That we happen to collapse every set of tens might just be a coincidence for all we know. The mere fact that we humans were able to use the symbol '0' for each such set of tens and the number in front of it as a count of how many times ten is a fascinating witness of human ingenuity. I.e. that 10 means 1 times ten things, 20 means two times ten things and 30 means 3 times ten things and so on and so forth. Even more interesting it becomes when we consider they expanded this way of thinking. They used a number in front of two zeros as a count of how many hundreds there were. I.e. that 100 means 1 times a hundred things, 200 means two times a hundred things and 300 means three times a hundred things and so on and so forth. Of course, humans, exploring as they are, did not stop there. They went on with a number in front of three zeros as a count for how many thousands there were and they did not stop continuing giving larger and larger quantities names. But where did it all stop? Logically there is no limit to counting other than time and things that are limiting the process.

But what about the collapsing process? The sets in an extraterrestrial mathematics that is aimed for inter-galactic conversation could use different kinds of zeros still, zeroes that reflected a primitive-way of representing their main base, like the ones depicted in the following graphic:

The resulting numbers would look as follows:

$$I\text{O} = 2, II\text{O} = 4, III\text{O} = 6, IIII\text{O} = 8, \dots n\text{O}$$

$$I\text{O} = 3, II\text{O} = 6, III\text{O} = 9, IIII\text{O} = 12, \dots n\text{O}$$

$$I\text{O} = 4, II\text{O} = 8, III\text{O} = 12, IIII\text{O} = 16, \dots n\text{O}$$

$$I\text{O} = 5, II\text{O} = 10, III\text{O} = 15, IIII\text{O} = 20, \dots n\text{O}$$

$$I\text{O} = 6, II\text{O} = 12, III\text{O} = 18, IIII\text{O} = 24, \dots n\text{O}$$

$$I\text{O} = 7, II\text{O} = 14, III\text{O} = 21, IIII\text{O} = 28, \dots n\text{O}$$

$$I\text{O} = 8, II\text{O} = 16, III\text{O} = 24, IIII\text{O} = 32, \dots n\text{O}$$

$$I\text{O} = 9, II\text{O} = 18, III\text{O} = 27, IIII\text{O} = 36, \dots n\text{O}$$

$$I\text{O} = 10, II\text{O} = 20, III\text{O} = 30, IIII\text{O} = 40, \dots n\text{O}$$

Of course this is not efficient as symbols, and thus they would not use it themselves. Just like we do not use it ourselves. But for a first-encounter with another species, this form

would be very efficient. We also have to keep in mind they may not write vertical lines I, II, III but horizontal lines just like the Chinese do for there first three numbers 一, 二, 三.

If we now try to imagine what an extraterrestrial table in base 6 may look like, of course with other than Arabic-numerals, it may look like this:

I	II	^	Y	Σ	I0
III	IIII	II^	IIY	IIΣ	II0
^I	^II	^^	^Y	^Σ	^0
YI	YII	Y^	YY	YΣ	Y0
ΣI	ΣII	Σ^	ΣY	ΣΣ	Σ0
0I	0II	0^	0Y	0Σ	00

Interesting is that we don't have to write I00 for 36 in base 10, but can only write 00. There is no need to have 'I' in front of the zero-symbols, as they already contain quantities > 1 and thus containing 1, or here denoted as 'I'.

Surely this is just mere speculation. But we encourage the reader to think of such possibilities, if there ever happens to be any encounter at all, given time-frames and cosmological distances and life-expectancies of host-stars we are more than lucky if the communication is one-way (where we listen but not answer) and two-way communication (where we listen but and answer) is hard to think of for practical reasons given by A. Einstein and J. C. Maxwell.

How we humans can use the Extraterrestrial-Zero-System (EZS) meaningfully in our own works

Instead of using the zeroes as mentioned above with dots, we could inscribe within them our symbols. With the exception of the number ten (10), that already uses zero in the hitherto classical way.

We observe eleven distinct zeroes with our Arabic-numerals inscribed into them. The first zero-symbol denotes the empty-set (\emptyset). And if used alongside any other base-system it is not to be understood as the empty-set, but the transition from positive, actual quantities, into negative, actually 'lacking' or directionally 'reversed' quantities (like we use in physics).

The number ten (10) must be written as ' $\textcircled{5}$ '. As described above, this is done to circumvent the confliction of the empty set with non-empty sets.

$$1 \times \textcircled{0} = 1,$$

$$2 \times \textcircled{0} = 2,$$

$$3 \times \textcircled{0} = 3,$$

$$4 \times \textcircled{0} = 4,$$

$$5 \times \textcircled{0} = 5,$$

$$6 \times \textcircled{0} = 6,$$

$$7 \times \textcircled{0} = 7,$$

$$8 \times \textcircled{0} = 8,$$

$$9 \times \textcircled{0} = 9,$$

$$10 \times \textcircled{0} = \textcircled{5}$$

And this continues as follows with 2 :

$$1 \times 2 = 2,$$

$$2 \times 2 = 4,$$

...

$$10 \times 2 = 20$$

Such it continues for 3 :

$$1 \times 3 = 3,$$

$$2 \times 3 = 6,$$

...

$$10 \times 3 = 30$$

For 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 it continues the same way. But for

$10 \times 0 = 00$ as two such zeroes are the same as a square. I.e. 00 equates to what we in our classical base 10 system would write as 10^2 . This is true for the other zero-systems as well. For example $33 = 9$ or to 3^2 in the usual base 10 system. And $77 = 49$ or 7^2 in the usual base 10 system.

This creates a notation challenge if we think about numbers like $n \times 7^{80}$, we would have to write 80 distinct 7's.

But we can easily bypass the problem by using almost the usual exponent notation $n \times 7^{80}$

Here a little bit bigger for visibility matters (the visibility gets worse if formatted):

$$7^{80}$$

The number-line extends as well and all numbers on it can be written as far as we humans have symbols for them, like in logographic languages we have symbols for numbers 0-9 for quantities in base 10. But if one is logical about it, one sees 10 is no new symbol in the sense 0-9 are symbols. Ten or written out '10' is a combination of '1' and '0'. But here '0' is confusing, because it simultaneously denotes the empty-set and a set of ten distinct one-quantities if a '1' is written in front of it. Our new number-line does not contribute to such a confusion.

$$\dots -9 -8 -7 -6 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 \dots$$

As we see the numbers could be written as well without the 0-symbol around them, like we are used to classically: $-\infty \dots, -10, -9, -8, -7, -6, -5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 \dots +\infty$. But '0' now really does resemble only the empty-set as a transition from positive to negative, or vice versa. It first becomes interesting after we have exhausted all our symbols. Then the number-line with the zero-systems has also vertical-lines with combinatorial representations, consisting of the symbols we do have inscribed into zeroes.

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